

Review of *The Weight of Reasons: A Framework for Ethics*, by Chris Tucker

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The notion of a normative reason, which has played a central role in normative and meta-normative theorizing in recent decades, appears closely tied to the idea of weight. Reasons are considerations that count in favor of or against actions and attitudes with a certain strength or weight, and they can be weighed against one another. Moreover, it is widely assumed that other normative verdicts—for instance, about what we ought to do—depend on truths about the relative weights of reasons. Chris Tucker’s *The Weight of Reasons* aims to provide a comprehensive examination of this issue, one that takes the metaphors of weight and weighing seriously. The book advances two central claims. The first, which I’ll call *Multiple Scales*, is that the fundamental model of weighing reasons employs more than one scale. The second, stronger claim—*Weight Pluralism*—is that reasons have at least two independent weights. The bulk of the book is devoted to the distinction between what Tucker and others call *justifying* and *requiring* weight. Later in the book, however, it becomes clear that at least one additional kind of weight—*commending* weight—must also be assumed. (I should note that Tucker uses the term ‘Weight Pluralism’ to refer to the weaker claim that reasons have at least two non-equivalent weight values, which allows for these values to depend on each other. But since the book actually defends the stronger and more interesting claim, it facilitates discussion to use it in the proposed way.)

Roughly speaking, chapters 1–5 and 9 are concerned with *Multiple Scales*, while chapters 6–8 defend and develop *Weight Pluralism*. The basic argument for *Multiple Scales* is that the fundamental model of weighing reasons should be neutral on substantive normative

assumptions about the weights certain reasons have, and that only a model with multiple scales can preserve this neutrality. The basic argument for *Weight Pluralism* is an inference to the best explanation of certain moral phenomena, in particular supererogation.

The book opens in Chapter 1 with the idea that a reason's weight is tied to its functional role, namely, to "push an act toward (im)permissibility, that is, ... make an act (im)permissible in the absence of sufficiently weighty countervailing considerations" (27). Tucker goes so far as to claim that "to be a reason is, by definition, to be something that pushes an act toward (im)permissibility" (30), but he promises to rely only on the weaker assumption that something is a reason if and only if it plays this functional role (cf. 29).

Starting from this assumption, Tucker introduces what he calls the "standard" (42) model of balancing reasons: Single Scale. Single Scale has two pans, representing an action, ϕ , and its alternative, $\neg\phi$. Any reason in favor of ϕ pushes the ϕ -pan down toward permissibility, and simultaneously pushes the $\neg\phi$ -pan up toward impermissibility. Conversely, a reason in favor of $\neg\phi$ pushes the $\neg\phi$ -pan down toward permissibility and the ϕ -pan up toward impermissibility.

This model, Tucker points out, entails that reasons play two functional roles that can be identified with a justifying and a requiring weight: By pushing an act toward permissibility, thereby tending to justify it, every reason also pushes the act's alternative toward impermissibility, thereby tending to require its omission. For Tucker, the problem is that Single Scale involves the controversial assumption that the justifying and the requiring weight of a reason are dependent variables – an assumption that rules out Weight Pluralism.

Consider, for example, what Tucker tendentiously calls "the standard account of supererogation" (43). This account attempts to explain why omitting the supererogatory act is permitted but not required by appeal to the hypothesis that reasons of self-interest have

merely justifying and no requiring weight. This view cannot be represented by Single Scale, as Single Scale entails that requiring weight and justifying weight necessarily come in the same proportion. The view can be represented by Tucker's Dual Scale model, however. According to Dual Scale, there is one scale to determine what is permitted and another scale to determine what is required. The Permission Scale weighs the justifying reasons for φ against the requiring reasons for $\neg\varphi$, while what Tucker calls the "Commitment Scale" weighs the requiring reasons for φ against the justifying reasons for $\neg\varphi$. This model allows for the assumption that reasons of self-interest have merely justifying weight, thus making room for the mentioned account of supererogation.

Now, as Tucker admits, there may well be plausible alternative explanations of supererogation that are not based on Weight Pluralism (116). He argues, however, that we should reject Single Scale in favor of a multiple scale model even if Weight Pluralism is false, at least insofar as we are looking for what he calls "the fundamental model of weighing reasons." In his view, such a model should "abstract away from particular judgments about what weight(s) a given reason has" (125). Since Single Scale makes a controversial substantive assumption about the relation between justifying and requiring weights, it cannot be the fundamental model – even if that assumption is true. Dual Scale is more neutral in this regard and therefore preferable. (Eventually, Tucker opts for a Dynamic Scale model, which involves a separate scale for every alternative, but for much of what this book is about, this complication can be ignored.)

The dialectic between Single and Dual Scale occupies most of chapters 1, 3 and 4. Chapter 2 defends scale models of weighing reasons against objections that are based on the holist assumption that the existence and weight of reasons is context-sensitive, while chapter 5 discusses the relation between reasons for and reasons against as well as various related

issues concerning the individuation of options and the ways in which reasons and weights may vary with the alternatives (issues often discussed under the headings ‘maximalism’, ‘contrastivism’ and ‘comparativism’).

Chapter 6 raises objections to Weight Monism – the view that “reasons have just a single weight value” (7) – while Chapters 7 and 8 develop Weight Pluralism in a way that addresses these and further challenges. At bottom, the discussion centers on puzzles concerning supererogation and the normative significance of small improvements. Before revisiting the book’s achievements in Chapter 10, Chapter 9 completes the discussion of weighing models by extending the Dual Scale model to cases involving more than two options.

The Weight of Reasons provides a clear and systematic analysis of weighing models, developing and defending a sophisticated pluralist position that will likely serve as a key reference for future work in the field. Though challenging at times, the book remains accessible even when addressing highly abstract and complex issues.

While the book’s analytical rigor is an undeniable strength, a notable weakness is its lack of sensitivity toward opposing views. This is apparent in several respects. To begin with, it neither mentions nor discusses the potential costs of Weight Pluralism. Rather than addressing such concerns, Tucker repeatedly suggests that Weight Monism is “accepted by faith, not argument” (129), or that “the main reason that ethicists tend to assume Weight Monism” is that “they don’t know how to think with” the justifying/requiring weight distinction – a distinction they “don’t understand [...] well enough” (9; cf. also 51; 344–5).

One worry I would have liked to see addressed is that the assumption of different and independent kinds of weights seems in conflict with ordinary normative thought. Paradigmatic deliberation is concerned with judgments like “There is more/most reason to do this” rather

than judgments like “There is more requiring reason to do this rather than justifying reason to do that”. If Weight Pluralism is true, judgements of the former kind are “unclear at best” (278). Weight Pluralism thus appears to carry the revisionary implication that standard deliberation is misguided, insofar as it rests on systematically unclear notions and overlooks important distinctions. We cannot, of course, dismiss this possibility from the outset. Still, there is good reason to prefer explanations with less revisionary import, not least because the case for Weight Pluralism proceeds by inference to the best explanation from common-sense moral commitments.

A second worry is that Weight Pluralism seems to be in tension with other philosophical ambitions, particularly the “Deontic Buckpassing” project, which seeks to provide informative analyses of the deontic in terms of reasons. Part of the appeal of this approach is its aim to unify deontic normativity through a single reason relation. But Tucker’s book claims that there are at least three distinct reason relations: justifying, requiring, and commending. Moreover, these relations are partly defined in deontic terms. Tucker seems to think that these conceptual definitions do not preclude the metaphysical priority of reasons (cf. 28). Yet deontic buckpassers might also aim for conceptual analysis. And even if they do not, it remains unclear how a reductive account of the properties of being required and being permitted in terms of requiring and justifying reasons could distinguish these reasons without using deontic vocabulary. In any case, such an account would be less unified and less informative than what deontic buckpassers typically seek. Perhaps the arguments for Weight Pluralism show that the Deontic Buckpassing project must be abandoned. However, the theoretical merits of a unified and informative explanation of the deontic in terms of reasons should not be discounted when judging whether the weight-pluralist explanation of normative phenomena is indeed superior to rival approaches.

The book's limited receptivity to opposing perspectives also shows in its tendency to overstate the force of its arguments. In his conclusion, Tucker declares that "Weight Pluralism is the runaway winner in its competition with Weight Monism" (344). Yet the argument he actually offers in Chapter 6 is far from compelling. In essence, the argument is that weight monists cannot explain certain cases of supererogation—specifically, the verdict that it is permissible to buy a car for oneself rather than donate the same amount to a charity that would predictably save five lives. Tucker acknowledges that monists could accommodate this verdict, provided they could plausibly appeal to the assumption that the reasons to buy the car and to donate the money are incommensurable (i.e., incomparable, not precisely comparable, or "on a par") (229–30). Nor does he reject incommensurability per se (234). However, he contends that the reasons in question cannot be incommensurable, because "it is far better to save five lives than to get the self-interested benefits of the car" (230).

It is surprising how weak this objection is, especially since it is the only objection to Weight Monism that Tucker actually defends and endorses in the book (as Tucker concedes, the remaining objections can all be met by allowing for incommensurability). Monists can grant that it is *impersonally better* to donate the money, and also that it is *morally better* (in the sense of being supported by the preponderance of moral reasons), while insisting that there is another normatively relevant sense of 'better' in which it is better to buy the car—namely, it is better for you. What is better for you correlates with agent-relative, prudential reasons that can compete with your moral reasons, including your agent-neutral reasons for promoting the impersonal good. Sidgwick's dualism of practical reason suggests that such reasons are always incommensurable—an assumption that Parfit and others have convincingly argued is too strong. Yet we need not go so far to maintain that they are incommensurable in the cases of supererogation that Tucker discusses, such as the car

example. Once we recognize that ‘better’ admits of several relevant senses, Tucker’s appeal to the betterness of saving lives loses much of its apparent force.

Finally, Tucker’s treatment shows no engagement with a wide array of alternative explanations of the deontic phenomena in question. While it demonstrates how Weight Pluralism can account for these phenomena, it does not establish that these explanations are superior to all relevant alternatives.

To see this, note that in addition to *direct views*, which link a requirement to ϕ with reasons for and against ϕ -ing and alternatives to ϕ -ing, there are also *indirect views*, which link requirements with other reasons, such as reasons for punishment (Mill), reasons for blame and guilt (Gibbard, Darwall), reasons for the act of requiring (Bedke), reasons to make amends (Rowland), or, which is my own preferred view, reasons for prescriptive expectations (for references, see Benjamin Kiesewetter, “What We May Expect of Each Other,” *Ethics* 136, 297–328 [2026]). Such indirect views offer greater flexibility than direct monist views in accounting for the phenomena in question, and arguably provide as much flexibility as pluralist direct views.

Where the pluralist will say that the supererogatory act is favored by justifying or commending reasons, but not by requiring reasons, proponents of indirect views will say that the act is favored by moral reasons for action, but not subject to the relevant indirect reasons. Importantly, however, indirect views do not need to assume that reasons can have different weights. They only assume what we already know: that reasons can have different objects. As a result, they are less revisionary than Weight Pluralism and compatible with Deontic Buckpassing, just like direct monist views. Given that these views are relatively widespread, one would expect an abductive argument for Weight Pluralism to engage with them. Yet Tucker’s book does not even mention the possibility of such views.

Tucker might hold that indirect views are implicitly addressed. At various points, he argues that, by his own functionalist definition, everything that “pushes toward” a requirement to φ is thereby a requiring reason to φ , and everything that “pushes toward” a permission to φ is thereby a justifying reason to φ (cf. 157; 163–4). On this basis, he argues that various direct views that appear to constitute *alternatives to Weight Pluralism*, are actually *variants of Weight Pluralism*. Consider, for example, the Dual Ranking View, according to which moral requirements are in place if and only if an action is favored by both the balance of moral reasons and the balance of all reasons. On the face of it, this view relies on the familiar distinction between moral and non-moral reasons and does not presuppose that reasons can have more than one weight value. But since on the Dual Ranking View, non-moral reasons can make actions morally permissible but not morally required, Tucker claims that it is committed to Weight Pluralism (cf. 164). (In fact, he would likely maintain that monists cannot avail themselves of the response to the car case outlined above since it presupposes something like the Dual Ranking View, which he takes to entail pluralism.) We find similar arguments concerning views that understand moral requirements in terms of the distinction between reasons-for and reasons-against (cf. 157) or views that explain supererogation in terms of agent-relative value (cf. 230, n. 9). These arguments suggest that Tucker would hold the same about indirect views. If requirements are linked to reasons for reactive attitudes, for example, then these reasons “push toward” requirements and are thereby, by Tucker’s definition, reasons for the required response.

There are weighty reasons, however, to resist this move – both with respect to direct views like the Dual Ranking View and indirect ones. Let me start with a point about the Dual Ranking View. Even granting Tucker’s functionalist definitions, dual ranking theorists can maintain that the “justifying weight” of non-moral reasons for morally favored actions is

nothing over and above the “requiring weight” they have for alternatives. (Note that the fact that this “requiring weight” is not “morally requiring weight” does not change the fact that the justifying weight entirely depends on requiring weight.) So even granting functionalism, the Dual Ranking View does not entail Weight Pluralism understood as the claim that there are *independent* weight values, but only the more or less trivial claim that reasons that are in the business of making an act required are *ipso facto* also in the business of making the alternatives not required (which, in turn, is really just another way of saying that they *compete* or *conflict* with reasons that are in the business of making alternatives required).

Second, insofar as Tucker’s functionalist definitions entail that apparent alternatives to Weight Pluralism are merely variants of it, that result only shows how misleading those definitions are. In themselves, neither the distinction between moral and non-moral reasons nor the distinction between reasons for actions and reasons for attitudes presupposes more than a single weight value. Why, then, would a view that explains moral requirements solely in terms of facts about such reasons be committed to Weight Pluralism? If we stipulate functional definitions that force this result, we only risk losing sight of important differences—for example, between saying that reasons can have different sources, different objects, or different kinds of weight.

Third, the functionalist definitions are independently highly controversial, as the literature on so-called explanationist accounts of normative reasons makes clear. Tucker neither engages with that literature nor offers an argument or defense of his functionalism. It is unclear why he should feel entitled, on this basis, to rule out *prima facie* attractive theoretical possibilities, such as an indirect monist view. Indirect views essentially claim that things that are not reasons to ϕ can nevertheless have the function of making ϕ -ing required, and are thus inconsistent with Tucker’s functional definitions. Tucker must either redescribe

such views in terms of requiring reasons or reject them. But redescribing them mischaracterizes them, and rejecting them on the basis of a stipulative definition begs the question.

Finally, arguments for Weight Pluralism that rely on functionalist definitions cannot support a substantive form of Weight Pluralism—on which plural weights play a non-redundant explanatory role—but at best a formal form, on which plural weights may be explanatorily idle. Formal Weight Pluralism does not support many of the book’s claims. It does not sustain the thesis that there is an important and largely neglected distinction between different weights (cf. 6–7), over and above the familiar moral/non-moral distinction and other familiar distinctions that do not themselves entail plural weights. Nor does it show that talk and thought about reasons *simpliciter* are problematic (cf. 278), since it is consistent with holding that everything of importance can be said without appealing to plural weights. And because formal Weight Pluralism is compatible with the view that distinctions between kinds of weight are entirely derivative from more fundamental differences, it cannot be used to support the claim that the fundamental model of weighing reasons contains more than one scale. If Weight Pluralism is true only by virtue of functionalist definitions, many of the conclusions drawn from it are unwarranted.

Tucker’s functionalism even seems to undercut his neutrality argument for Multiple Scales – an argument intended to stand independently of Weight Pluralism. For, if functionalism is correct, any first-order normative view that assigns independent, plural weights to reasons is compatible with a merely formal version of Weight Pluralism, on which those multiple weights are explained by single weights of different kinds of reasons. Any substantive normative view should therefore be compatible with the thesis that the *fundamental* model of weighing reasons employs a single scale. It follows from this

that the single scale model does not rule out any substantive normative views. But then Tucker's neutrality argument for Multiple Scales fails. The argument was that single-scale models violate neutrality because they exclude views that assign independent, plural weights to reasons. Given functionalism, however, single-scale models do not exclude those views.

There has been a growing interest in Weight Pluralism, and Tucker's book offers a timely intervention in this debate. It will be essential reading for those concerned with pluralist models of weighing reasons and pluralist explanations of moral phenomena, as Tucker undertakes the difficult task of articulating and developing these ideas in depth. That said, readers should be aware that the book relies on controversial background assumptions that steer the argument in directions that a more balanced starting point would not. In my opinion, Weight Pluralism appears to be the "runaway winner" in this book only because Tucker excludes its strongest competitors from the race.

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